

DEVELOPMENT OF HIGH-PERFORMANCE BIPOLAR PLATES BY ELECTRODE INTEGRATION FOR VANADIUM REDOX FLOW BATTERIES

Amanpreet Kaur¹ and Jun Woo Lim²

¹Graduate School of Flexible and Printable Electronics & LANL-JBNU Engineering Institute-Korea, Jeonbuk National University, 567 Baekje-daero, Deokjin-gu, Jeonju-si, Jeonbuk State, 54896, Republic of Korea

Email: amankhamano@gmail.com, web page: <https://ascl.jbnu.ac.kr>

²Graduate School of Flexible and Printable Electronics & LANL-CBNU Engineering Institute Korea & Department of Mechatronics Engineering & JBNU-KIST Industry-Academia Convergence Research, Jeonbuk National University, 567 Baekje-daero, Deokjin-gu, Jeonju-si, Jeonbuk State, 54896, Republic of Korea

Email: jul170@jbnu.ac.kr, web page: <https://ascl.jbnu.ac.kr>

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ABSTRACT

The bipolar plate is a crucial element of the vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) as it serves as both the electrical path for the electrolyte and the structural support for the cell within the VRFB stack. The graphite material has been used as the bipolar plate, mostly due to its excellent electrical conductivity. A significant limitation of the VRFB is the presence of several core components. Hence, the internal contact resistance (ICR) arises between the electrode and bipolar plate within the cell stack, and it is significantly greater than the bulk resistance of the corresponding specimens. This study focuses on creating an integrated assembly of the electrode and bipolar plate to address the limitations of the ICR. The integrated assembly was constructed using a single carbon felt specimen. The study resulted in the development of an electrode-integrated BP that exhibited a 28% decrease in overall resistance and a 175% improvement in mechanical properties. Gas permeability and acid aging tests confirmed that the electrode-integrated BP exhibited zero gas permeability and was therefore durable. In conclusion, a two-cell charge/discharge test confirmed that the energy efficiency of the integrated structure had increased by 6.3%. The proposed integrated structure is thus a potentially advantageous substitute for conventional BP and CF electrode assemblies.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest in using renewable resources for power production due to environmental concerns about the usage of non-renewable resources like fossil fuels [1,2]. Solar and wind energy are highly accessible, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly sources of energy [3,4]. Nevertheless, the generation of power from these renewable energy sources is irregular, requiring the development of large electrical energy storage systems [5]. This issue has led to significant progress in the research and development of electrical energy storage devices, particularly in the past few decades. Vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB) show great potential as energy storage systems due to their optimum combination of safety, durability, stability, and efficiency. A standard Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRFB) consists of several cells, two pumps, and two electrolyte tanks. The structure of each cell consists of two bipolar plates (BPs), two electrodes, and a membrane.

The membrane acts as a barrier between the two half-cells in the VRFB. The electrode facilitates the formation of reactive sites and electrical pathways for the electrolyte. It is often made of carbon and graphite felt. The VRFB stores energy in the two electrolytes containing different redox couples, V^{2+}/V^{3+} and VO^{2+}/VO_2^+ , which generate a potential difference through an electrochemical redox reaction. This

results in a charge-discharge reaction. The BPs provide pathways for electrical current to flow between adjacent cells while also isolating each individual cell. Consequently, a BP must possess certain characteristics, including a high electrical conductivity, a low permeability of vanadium sulfuric acid electrolytes, and chemical stability. Although VRFB (Vanadium Redox Flow Battery) is being more commercialized, there is still a persistent requirement to investigate further methods of improving efficiency and lowering expenses. The power capacity of the VRFB is governed by the size of the stack area and the number of stacks, while the energy capacity is dictated by the quantity of electrolyte. In the case of a multiple-stack VRFB, improving cell resistance might lead to enhanced performance.

In VRFB, there is a contact between the Bipolar Plate (BP) and electrode in the VRFB. This interface gives rise to problems associated with interfacial resistance (ICR) as shown on Fig. 1. In order to address these ICR (Internal Cell Resistance) difficulties, it is necessary to apply a high compaction pressure to the VRFB (Vanadium Redox Flow Battery) stack. However, the VRFB experiences a low applied pressure due to structural constraints, resulting in a decrease in viscous dissipation. Therefore, the internal contact resistance (ICR) has a substantial impact on the cell efficiency of the vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) and causes a reduction in efficiency. Lim et al. proposed an integrated structure of a carbon felt electrode (CFE) and BP for VRFB, which was created by local thermoplastic welding [6]. The structure of the CFE-BP assembly demonstrated a decrease in electrical resistance and an increased level of energy efficiency due to the reduction in contact resistance. However, the mechanical characteristics of the CFE can be compromised because to the reduction in porosity caused by the compaction pressure applied during the production process.

Figure 1: Schematic of vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) and interfacial contact resistance.

We proposed a carbon felt electrode (CFE)-BP-Carbon felt electrode (CFE) (CFE-BP-CFE) composite structure that generates repetitive units of multi-cell arrays from a single CF in order to overcome these issues. By utilizing this approach, the degradation of mechanical properties caused by the compressive pressure of the CF electrode is prevented. The CFE-BP-CFE composite structure was

fabricated using one single CF in order to reduce contact resistance between the CFE and BP, as well as adjacent cells; this structure established an electrode-BP-electrode interconnection with the CF fibers. By partially impregnating the electrode section with a soluble resin, the CFE section, which measured 4 mm in thickness from both surfaces of a 10 mm single CF, was rendered impermeable. This impregnated CFE section was protected from the compaction pressure utilized during BP fabrication. Significant hydrophilicity was achieved by thermal treatment, enabling the electrode section to be filled with regular glucose and porosity to be eliminated under CF pressure. Following this fabrication, a two-cell test was conducted to evaluate the total resistance, gas permeability, and charge/discharge cycle of the battery.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTIONS

2.1 Fabrication of the integrated structure

The CFE-BP-CFE integrated structure was fabricated from the single CF. The properties of the CF are shown in Table 1. The assembly is prepared in the compression mold. The carbon felt electrode portion is filled with the regular glucose to secure it from the pressure of the compression mold. The bipolar plate portion is fabricated by the epoxy resin by partial impregnation in the vacuum oven and subsequently in compression mold. The detailed procedure of fabrication is shown in Fig. 2.

Thickness	Density	Tensile strength	Porosity
10 mm	0.08 g/cm ³	0.15 MPa	92-94%

Table 1. Properties of carbon felt.

Figure 2: Experimental procedure of the carbon felt electrode-bipolar plate-carbon felt electrode (CFE-BP-CFE) composite structure.

2.2 Characterizations

The areal specific resistance has been calculated using the four-point probe method. The permeability of the CFE-BP-CFE composite structure was measured using gas sensors. Acid-aging test has been conducted to check the stability of the bipolar plate. Charge-discharge test was carried out to check the performance of the integrated assembly of the electrode and bipolar plater for VRFB. The setup pf charge discharge test using integrated structure is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Schematic of core components of two-cell assembly: (a) Current collector; (b) Bipolar plate-carbon felt electrode (BP-CFE) composite structure; (c) Flow frame; (d) Membrane; (e) Carbon felt electrode-bipolar plate-carbon felt electrode (CFE-BP-CFE) composite structure.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An optical microscope image of the 4-mm-thick impregnated layer is presented in Fig. 4(a). The same procedure was applied to the opposite side of the CF. Fig. 4(b) displays the CF with glucose partially impregnated from both sides. Fig. 4(c) presents optical microscope images of the cross-section of the fabricated CFE-BP-CFE composite structure. The central region, corresponding to the bipolar plate (BP), shows uniform epoxy impregnation. Notably, Fig. 4(c) reveals the presence of interconnected carbon fibers bridging the BP and CFE layers. These fiber connections establish a continuous electrical pathway between adjacent cells, thereby improving the overall electrical conductivity of the integrated BP-CFE structure.

Figure 4: Optical microscope images: (a) Thickness of glucose in partially impregnated carbon felt (CF) as a function of immersion time; (b) Cross-section of carbon felt electrode (CFE) showing glucose impregnation from both sides; (c) Cross-section of the CFE-BP-CFE composite structure.

Figure 5 demonstrates the overall resistance of three structures: the conventional structure with commercial graphite composite BP, the CFE, and the designed CFE-BP-CFE composite structure. As expected, the total electrical resistance decreased in proportion to the increase in compaction pressure. The total resistance of the CFE-BP-CFE composite structure was measured to be about equivalent to

that of the CFE. However, the resistance of the CFE was found to be 28% lower than that of the conventional construction. The reason for this is that the CFE-BP-CFE composite structure consists of a single CFE, and both surfaces of the CFEs are consistently linked with carbon fibers through the central BP section.

Figure 5: Total resistance of CF, Integrated structure and Conventional structure.

Figure 6 demonstrates the results of the charge/discharge test for both the integrated and conventional assemblies using a two-cell VRFB configuration. The galvanostatic charge/discharge test of the integrated structure demonstrated a reduced discharge voltage and a higher charge voltage. The energy and voltage efficiency of the CFE-BP-CFE composite structure two-cell assembly were enhanced by a significant 6.3%. The decrease in the Ohmic loss in the cell was attributed to the integration of BP and CFEs, resulting in a reduction in the total resistance of the cell. The performance of the CFE-BP-CFE composite structure was improved by the interconnected fibers of BP and CFEs, which created continuous electrical paths. However, the coulombic efficiency remained constant for both setups.

Figure 6: Charge discharge curve of Integrated structure and Conventional structure.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the development of a composite structure consisting of a CFE-BP-CFE configuration, achieved through the utilization of a novel fabrication technique that effectively addresses the issue of ICR. The electrode and BP parts were linked together using carbon fibers, since the integrated structure was created from a single sheet of carbon fiber (CF). The proposed structure demonstrated a 28% reduction in resistance compared to the standard structure, which was roughly equivalent to the resistance of a single CFE. Additionally, the charge/discharge test conducted on the suggested construction with two cells showed a longer duration for both charging and discharging, as well as a 6.3% improvement in energy efficiency compared to the conventional structure. This improvement can be attributed to a decrease in Ohmic potential and a reduction in total resistance. The CFE-BP-CFE composite structure minimizes the quantity of core components in the VRFB stack while preserving the stack's efficiency through the use of lower compaction pressure. Hence, the created CFE-BP-CFE composite structure has the potential to serve as a substitute for traditional VRFB components, offering enhanced performance. Furthermore, the VRFB system can be successfully commercialized based on its economic and engineering viability.

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